

Cohesive Energies and the Relative Stabilities of the First Row Transition Metal Fluorides

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With the help of a modified form of Kapustinskii-Yatsimirskii's equation, cohesive energies of the first-row transition-metal fluoride crystals have been computed. The standard heats of formation and the relative stabilities of the fluorides in different valence states have been calculated and found to agree with several of the experimental observations.

THE lattice energies of the first-row transition-metal halides were calculated earlier¹ using one of the Kapustinskii's equations based upon the inverse-power potential². An empirical form of lattice energy equation employing the use of a logarithmic form of potential has recently been proposed³ as given by :

$$U_L(\text{Kcal/mole}) = \frac{287.2 \sum n Z_1 Z_2}{(r_c + r_a)} \left[1 - \log_{10} \left\{ 1 + \frac{p}{(r_c + r_a)^2} \right\} \right] + 2.5 \sum n Z_1 Z_2 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where r_c or r_a is the radius of the cation or the anion in an octahedral environment of oppositely charged ions; $p = 2\text{\AA}^2$, and the other terms have their usual meanings.

The above equation has been found to yield satisfactory results in the case of a large number of ionic crystals³⁻⁶. We extend our calculations to derive the cohesive energies of the first-row transition-metal fluorides and study their relative stabilities.

Results and Discussion

Under the influence of the electrostatic field of the neighbouring negative ions or ligands, the d -orbitals of the metal ions undergo splitting and their degeneracy is lost. This splitting produces a stabilisation energy, Δ_o , and it is a measure of the crystal-field stabilisation energy, C.F.S.E. The Δ_o values for the difluorides are known from a recent source⁶. The pure $3d$ character of the orbitals will be affected due to the presence of $4S^1$ electron in the M^+ ions. The ligand field splitting will have low-values for the monofluorides. For them estimates vary between 10 to 30% of the Δ_o values for the difluorides. We have estimated Δ_o

values for monofluorides to be of the order of about 20% of the difluorides. For the trifluorides, Δ_o values are twice as much as the values for the difluorides. This is logical in view of the fact that Δ_o values for complexes in the first transition series range from 7,500-12,500 cm^{-1} for divalent ions and 14,000-25,000 cm^{-1} for trivalent ions⁷.

The cohesive energies of crystals, W , at 25° is obtained by adding appropriate Δ_o values to the U_L values given by :

$$W = U_L + \Delta_o + nRT \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The term nRT is the PV correction at 25°.

The heats of formation of the fluorides, $MF_n(c)$, can then be calculated from equn. (3) :

$$\Delta H_f^\circ MF_n(c) = \Delta H_f^\circ M^{n+}(g) + n \Delta H_f^\circ F^-(g) - W \quad (3)$$

where the terms have their usual significances.

Table 1 lists the input data for the ionic radii of the metal ions in different valence states, the crystal field stabilisation energies and the cohesive energies of the metal fluorides. Due to Jahn-Teller distortions proper estimates of r_c values for d^4 and d^9 ions have been made. The ionic radius of fluoride ion has been taken to be 1.36 \AA ⁸. The standard heats of formation of the F^- has been compiled from a recent source⁶. Table 2 lists the input data and the calculated as well as the experimental values for the standard heats of formation of the metal fluorides. It can be seen that the agreement between the two sets of values is satisfactory.

Enthalpies of Disproportionation :

The enthalpies of disproportionation of the

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following reactions have been calculated :

TABLE 1—RADII OF THE METAL IONS, C. F. S. E. AND COHESIVE ENERGIES OF TRANSITION METAL FLUORIDE CRYSTALS

Elements M	Ionic radii (Å)			Δ_o (C. F. S. E.) (K cal/mole)			W (K cal/mole)		
	M ⁺ (Ref. 1)*	M ²⁺ (Ref. 8)	M ³⁺ (Ref. 8)	MF(c) (Estimated)	MF ₂ (c) (Ref. 6)	MF ₃ (c) (Estimated)	MF(c) This work	MF ₂ (c) This work	MF ₃ (c) This work
Sc	1.06	1.00*	0.81	2	10	0	215	662	1377
Ti	0.96	0.90	0.76	5	25	20	225	695	1419
V	0.94	0.88	0.74	7	34	50	228	708	1458
Cr	0.90	0.84	0.69	5	27	68	229	709	1496
Mn	0.88	0.80	0.66	0	0	54	226	691	1498
Fe	0.80	0.76	0.64	3	13	0	236	713	1453
Co	0.85	0.74	0.63	4	22	26	232	726	1483
Ni	0.90	0.72	0.62	9	28	44	230	737	1506
Cu	0.96	0.70	0.60*	6	30	56	226	743	1527
Zn	0.88	0.74	0.60*	0	0	60	226	704	1531

TABLE 2—INPUT DATA, CALCULATED AND EXPERIMENTAL VALUES FOR STANDARD HEATS OF FORMATION OF METAL FLUORIDES IN KILO CALORIES PER MOLE

Elements M	$\Delta H_f^\circ M^+(g)$ (Ref. 8,9)	$\Delta H_f^\circ M^{2+}(g)$ (Ref. 8,9)	$\Delta H_f^\circ M^{3+}(g)$ (Ref. 8,9)	$\Delta H_f^\circ MF_n(c)$					
				MF(c)		MF ₂ (c)		MF ₃ (c)	
				Present work	Exptl. (Ref. 9)	Present work	Exptl. (Ref. 9,10)	Present work	Exptl. (Ref. 9,10)
Sc	244.3	539.5	1110.2	-31	—	-244	—	-448	-390
Ti	252.5	565.4	1214.3	-33	—	-251	-198	-363	-315
V	275.4	613.2	1298.1	-13	—	-216	—	-341	—
Cr	250.8	631.0	1346.0	-39	—	-199	-186	-332	-277
Mn	238.5	599.1	1337.1	-48	—	-213	-189	-342	—
Fe	281.7	654.8	1411.8	-13	—	-180	—	-223	—
Co	232.8	676.0	1448.1	-10	—	-171	-165	-216	-194
Ni	278.7	697.2	1507.8	-12	—	-161	-156	-180	—
Cu	259.9	726.8	1407.2	-28	-19	-137	-130	-301	—
Zn	247.8	661.9	1584.3	-39	—	-163	-183	-128	—

The calculated values have been listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3—ENTHALPIES OF DISPROPORTIONATION OF TRANSITION METAL FLUORIDES IN KILO CALORIES PER MOLE

Element	ΔH_1 Eqn. (4)	ΔH_2 Eqn. (5)	ΔH_3 Eqn. (6)	ΔH_4 Eqn. (7)	ΔH_5 Eqn. (8)
Sc	+31	-91	+213	-55	+204
Ti	+33	-92	+218	-6	+135
V	+13	-95	+203	-11	+125
Cr	+39	-60	+160	-22	+133
Mn	+48	-58	+165	-15	+129
Fe	+13	-77	+167	+31	+43
Co	+10	-75	+161	+33	+45
Ni	+12	-68	+149	+41	+19
Cu	+28	-40	+109	-64	+164
Zn	+39	-42	+124	+78	-35

From the table it is obvious that the monofluorides are stable to disproportionation into their elements, but they will change to the difluorides with the exception of CuF. In fact, CuF has been found to exist, whereas all the monofluorides from ScF to ZnF are non-existent. We also observe that the difluorides are stable to decomposition into monofluorides. CuF₂ is least stable among them and may decompose at high temperatures into CuF. The disproportionation of difluorides into trifluorides is possible barring FeF₂, CoF₂, NiF₂ and ZnF₂. CuF₂ will have a maximum tendency to be converted into CuF₃.

We again observe that barring ZnF₃, all the trifluorides are stable to dissociation into MF₂. The present data in Table 3 predict isolation of CuF₃.

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References

1. M. BARBER, J. W. LINNETT and N. H. TAYLOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3323.
2. A. F. KAPUSTINSKII, *Quart. Rev.*, 1956, **10**, 283.
3. L. THAKUR and A. K. SINHA, *Indian J. Pure and Appl. Phys.*, 1977, **15**, 794.
4. L. THAKUR, and B. B. SANDWAR, *Fertilizer Technol.*, 1978, **15**, in press.
5. L. THAKUR and B. B. SANDWAR, *Nat. Acad. Sc. Letters*, 1978, **1**, 171.
6. L. THAKUR, A. K. SINHA and B. B. SANDWAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17A**, 1.
7. M. DAY and J. SELBIN, "Theoretical Inorganic Chemistry", Affil. East-West Press, New Delhi, 1967, p. 291.
8. N. N. GREENWOOD, "Ionic Crystals, Lattice Defects and Non-Stoichiometry", Butterworths, London, 1968.
9. N. A. LANGR, "Hand-Book of Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1974.
10. D. D. WAGMAN, W. H. EVANS, V. B. PARKER, I. HALOW, S. M. BAILEY and R. H. SCHUMM, "Selected Values of Chemical Thermodynamic Properties, Technical Note 270-4", NBS, Washington, 1969.